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Influence of Ag co-activation on the Dy³⁺ luminescence in lithium tetraborate glasses

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Abstract. In this work we study and analyse the optical-luminescence properties of the lithium tetraborate (Li₂B₄O₇ or Li₂O–2B₂O₃) glasses activated with dysprosium (Dy) and co-activated with Dy and silver (Ag). Our analysis reveals the presence of Dy³⁺ (4f⁹) and Ag⁺ (4d¹⁰) ions as well as non-plasmonic Ag nanoclusters in the lithium tetraborate glass network. In the luminescence emission spectra were detected two strong and narrow blue and yellow bands attributed to Dy³⁺ ions as well as two broad unresolved bands covering violet-green spectral range, which correspond to Ag⁺ ions and Ag nanoclusters. An increase in the luminescence intensity of Dy³⁺ and an increase in the corresponding quantum yield as a result of Ag co-activation were obtained. Mechanisms underlying the energy transfer processes from Ag⁺ ions and Ag nanoclusters to Dy³⁺ ions have been discussed. Our results contribute to the development of the glassy luminescent materials for the white spectral range.

Keywords: borate glasses; luminescence; Dy³⁺ ions; Ag⁺ ions; Ag nanoclusters.

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1. Introduction

Lanthanides are known as a series of rare earth chemical elements in the periodic table with an unfilled $4f$ shell. Lanthanides are well-known for their very good luminescent properties, which involve the emission of light when the electrons make transition from higher to lower energy states. As a result, lanthanides are valuable in optoelectronic technologies such as light sources, lasers, scintillators, optical fibres, *etc.* [1,2].

Dysprosium (Dy) also has been implicated in a number of luminescent applications. In oxide compounds, dysprosium predominantly is present as Dy^{3+} ($4f^9$, $^6\text{H}_{15/2}$) ions. Luminescence of Dy^{3+} ions is typically located in the visible range of the electromagnetic spectrum and is caused by the $^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_J$ ($J = 15/2 - 9/2$) electronic transitions [2]. Dy^{3+} ions are known for having sharp and well-defined emission bands. The most intense emission bands of Dy^{3+} ions are located in the blue and yellow ranges and belong to the $^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_{15/2}$ and $^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow ^6\text{H}_{13/2}$ transitions, respectively.

It should be noted that there are few reports in the literature on the reduction of Dy^{3+} ions to Dy^{2+} ($4f^{10}$, $^5\text{I}_8$) ions. The Dy^{2+} ions can be obtained in strontium aluminate persistent phosphors [3] and some fluoride compounds [4]. In oxide glasses the Dy^{2+} ions have not been reported in the available literature. Therefore, in oxide glasses, only Dy^{3+} ions are considered as a possible main oxidation state for dysprosium.

Borate glasses offer superior technological advantages over borate crystals in the mass production of a wide variety of shapes and sizes. Compared to growing borate crystals, the production of borate glasses is faster, cheaper and easier [5,6]. Borate glasses can be activated with lanthanide ions in higher quantities than borate crystals. Last but not least, borate glasses can be easily formed into various shapes of glass products with the required geometries.

Properties of Dy^{3+} -activated borate glasses with different compositions have been reported in a number of works [7–16]. These works report the luminescence of Dy^{3+} ions in lithium borate [7,9,12], lithium fluoroborate [7,8], calcium borate [10], lithium calcium borate [10], lithium lead aluminium borate [11], multicomponent alkali and alkaline earth borate [13], lithium yttrium borate [14], lead borate [15], barium borate [16] and lithium aluminium borate [16] glasses. From the

results presented in [7–16] it can be concluded that Dy³⁺-activated borate glasses hold great promise for practical applications in luminescent devices, visible lasers and white LEDs.

The light output of the luminescence of rare earth ions, including Dy³⁺ ions, can be further enhanced by energy transfer from co-activators. This is very important because rare earth ions, including Dy³⁺ ions, have narrow and weak absorption bands due to parity forbidden $4f - 4f$ transitions. Co-activators with stronger and broader absorption can absorb the excitation energy and transfer it to the rare earth ions. This can lead to more powerful emission. At present time, an attractive concept for enhancing the luminescence of rare earth ions is silver (Ag) co-activation. In order to enhance the luminescence of rare earth ions in glasses, have been proposed three different mechanisms involving: 1) plasmonic Ag nanoparticles; 2) Ag⁺ ions; 3) non-plasmonic Ag nanoclusters [17].

The luminescence properties of glasses activated with Sm and co-activated with Sm and Ag with a basic composition of Li₂B₄O₇ were investigated in our study [18]. Intensified Sm³⁺ luminescence with an increase of the quantum yield of nearly 43% was observed in the Ag-co-activated sample. Such enhancement was assigned to the Ag⁺ ions → Sm³⁺ ions and Ag nanoclusters → Sm³⁺ ions energy transfer pathways [18]. It was summarised that Li₂B₄O₇:Sm,Ag glass is a perspective luminescent material in the orange-red spectral range. The main advantage of this glass is the simplicity of its preparation, which allows the production of huge transparent luminescent layers, which is not possible with powders and crystalline materials.

The origin of the energy levels is quite similar for Sm³⁺ ($4f^6$) and Dy³⁺ ($4f^9$) ions. Specifically, the ⁶H_J term is related to the ground term in Sm³⁺ and Dy³⁺. The difference is in the J value. The Sm³⁺ ground state is ⁶H_{5/2} (minimum J for a shell less than half-filled), whereas for Dy³⁺ it is ⁶H_{15/2} (maximum J for a shell more than half-filled). Therefore, luminescence properties of Dy-activated and Dy-Ag-co-activated Li₂B₄O₇ glasses need to be investigated in order to give answer on the following question: Can Ag co-activation in the lithium tetraborate glass lead to the enhancement of the Dy³⁺ luminescence, similarly to the Sm³⁺ luminescence reported in our article [18], or not?

The emission behaviour of Dy^{3+} ions in the presence of Ag co-activator up to now has been investigated in several different glass systems [19–26], such as silicate, phosphate, tellurite, and borate. These references in chronological order correspond to the following glass compositions: lanthanum potassium barium fluorosilicate [19], multicomponent aluminophosphate [20], sodium phosphate [21], lead borate [22], multicomponent tellurite [23], lithium sodium zinc phosphate [24], lithium strontium zinc borate [25], sodium aluminium borate [26]. The mechanism by which Dy–Ag interaction affects the Dy^{3+} luminescence differs significantly in the available literature. The phenomenon of energy transfer from Ag^+ to Dy^{3+} ions has been noticed in [19,24]. The prevalence of effects associated with Ag nanoparticles has been documented in [20–23,25,26]. In these articles [20–23,25,26], despite the presence of Ag nanoparticles, predicting the impact of Ag co-activation remains unpredictable. Studies in [21], [23], [25] and [26] report an enhancement of the Dy^{3+} luminescence, whereas results published in [20] and [22] show its quenching.

Hence, the available literature analysis suggests that it is not possible to predict the nature of the Dy-Ag interaction in advance. A separate study is essential to understand the effect of co-activation in each material. This is important because successful synergistic co-activation provides opportunities for the development of advanced materials for various optoelectronic applications. In this work we examine the influence of Ag co-activation on the optical-spectral properties of Dy^{3+} ions in lithium tetraborate glass ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$). Optical absorption, and photoluminescence (emission and excitation spectra, decay kinetics, quantum yield measurements) are used for this purpose. Focus of the presented article is to investigate the potential enhancement of the Dy^{3+} luminescence and the mechanisms underlying this enhancement.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Glass preparation

The preparation of Dy-activated and Dy-Ag-co-activated lithium tetraborate ($\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ or 1:2 ratio between Li_2O and B_2O_3) glasses was carried out by means of conventional melt quenching technology in an air atmosphere [27]. The first step was to obtain the pure (non-activated)

polycrystalline powder of lithium tetraborate. A stoichiometric mixture of Li_2CO_3 and H_3BO_3 was placed in a corundum crucible. The crucible containing the mixture was placed in a furnace. The preparation of lithium tetraborate was carried out according to several sequential chemical reactions, outlined as follows:

At the beginning of the second step, the lithium tetraborate powder was mixed thoroughly with 1.0 mol.% of Dy_2O_3 , or with 1.0 mol.% of Dy_2O_3 and 2.0 mol.% of AgNO_3 . Afterward, the obtained two mixtures were subjected to melting in corundum crucibles by heating to 1000°C in a furnace and maintaining this temperature for 30 minutes. The process was completed by rapid cooling of the melts, resulting in the formation of glasses – $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Dy}$ and $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7:\text{Dy,Ag}$. These glasses will be labelled below in the manuscript as $\text{LiBO}:\text{Dy}$ and $\text{LiBO}:\text{Dy,Ag}$, respectively. In preparation for optical absorption and luminescence measurements, the samples underwent cutting and polishing to dimensions in mm of $10 \times 6 \times 1$.

2.2. Research equipment

The Shimadzu UV-2600 spectrophotometer with an integrating sphere attachment was used to record optical absorption spectra. The Horiba FluoroMax-4 spectrofluorimeter was used to record luminescence emission and excitation spectra as well as luminescence decay kinetics. The Hamamatsu C9920-02G absolute PL quantum yield spectrometer was used to measure the luminescence quantum yield. All recordings were made at room temperature (about 295 K).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optical absorption spectroscopy

The optical absorption spectra of $\text{LiBO}:\text{Dy}$ and $\text{LiBO}:\text{Dy,Ag}$ glasses are presented in Fig. 1. Spectra are given in the absorbance scale because the thickness of the two samples was the same with an accuracy of 0.01 mm. The fundamental absorption edge of both glasses is observed in the

spectral range of 300–400 nm. The effect of Ag co-activation is a shift of the fundamental absorption edge to longer wavelengths around 4–6 nm (see Fig. 1). But, the absorption band associated with Ag co-activator was not clearly observed in Fig. 1. The absorption of Ag^+ ions, which is typically located in the UV range of the spectrum, is masked by the fundamental absorption edge.

Fig. 1. Optical absorption spectra of LiBO:Dy (a) and LiBO:Dy,Ag (b) glasses.

Let us look at the absorption of Dy^{3+} ions (see inset in Fig. 1). Four well-observed absorption bands peaking around 797 nm, 893 nm, 1079 nm, and 1255 nm according to [28] correspond to the ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{5/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{7/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{9/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{7/2}$, and ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{F}_{11/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$ transitions of Dy^{3+} ions. The weak band around 385 nm, which overlaps with the fundamental absorption edge, corresponds to the ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{F}_{7/2}$, ${}^4\text{I}_{13/2}$ transitions of Dy^{3+} ions. The weak absorption from 410 to 490 nm corresponds to the unresolved low-intensity ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{G}_{11/2}$, ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{I}_{15/2}$, and ${}^6\text{H}_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ transitions of Dy^{3+} ions. A similar almost unresolved shape of the visible Dy^{3+} absorption bands was observed previously in [8,14,23,24,25]. The absorption bands of Dy^{3+} ions in the infrared range

are much stronger than those in the visible range because they are spin allowed, whereas the transitions in the visible range are spin forbidden.

The absorption associated with surface plasmon resonance (SPR) of metallic Ag nanoparticles, which is typically located in the violet-blue range of the spectrum [18,20], is not clearly observed in Fig. 1. It can be seen that the absorption from 500 to 400 nm increases more in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass compared to LiBO:Dy glass. However, it is not convincing to draw firm conclusions from this. In our opinion, the formation of neutral Ag nanoparticles in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is unlikely.

Therefore, the optical absorption spectra of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses show characteristic intraconfigurational transitions of Dy^{3+} ions. But, the optical absorption spectroscopy does not allow to unambiguously identify the type of Ag centres in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass.

3.2. Luminescence emission and excitation spectra of Dy^{3+} ions

Luminescence emission spectra of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses recorded upon UV-A excitation ($\lambda_{exc} = 349$ nm) are presented in Fig. 2. There are two strong and few weak bands. Strong emission bands peaking at 481 nm (blue range) and 574 nm (yellow range) correspond to the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{15/2}$ and ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$ transitions of Dy^{3+} ions, respectively. Usually, the intensity of the yellow band (hypersensitive transition, $\Delta L = 2$, $\Delta J = 2$) is more influenced by the local environment of Dy^{3+} ions than the intensity of the blue band (non-hypersensitive transition). As a result, the yellow/blue intensity ratio (Y/B) for Dy^{3+} is often calculated in a similar way to the red/orange intensity ratio for Eu^{3+} . The Y/B ratio calculated from the peak intensities equals 1.28 and 1.27 for LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses, respectively, and according to [14,15] indicates the asymmetry of the local environment of Dy^{3+} ions in the investigated glasses. Observed weak emission bands peaking at 662 nm and 753 nm correspond to the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{11/2}$ and ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{9/2}$ transitions of Dy^{3+} ions, respectively. The intensity of the Dy^{3+} luminescence in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is about 15% higher than in LiBO:Dy glass, while the shape of the bands remains quite similar in both glasses. Maxima positions, bandwidths, and branching ratios (calculated from the integrated intensities in the wavenumber scale) of the emission bands associated with the ${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{11/2}$ ($J = 15/2 - 9/2$)

transitions are presented in Table 1. A small difference between the glasses is the bandwidth. The higher bandwidth in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass may be related to the higher structural disorder in this glass due to Ag co-activation.

Fig. 2. Luminescence emission spectra of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses recorded upon excitation at 349 nm.

Table 1. Position of maximum, λ_{\max} [nm], bandwidth, $\Delta\lambda$ [nm], and branching ratio (β) of the Dy^{3+} emission bands in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses.

Transitions	LiBO:Dy			LiBO:Dy,Ag		
	λ_{\max}	$\Delta\lambda$	β	λ_{\max}	$\Delta\lambda$	β
${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{15/2}$	481	17.2	0.533	481	17.6	0.540
${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$	574	15.4	0.452	574	15.6	0.444
${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{11/2}$	662	19.3	0.012	662	20.3	0.012
${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{9/2}$	753	14.8	0.003	753	17.6	0.004

In addition to the two strong and two weak bands discussed above, a weak narrow band peaking at 452 nm is observed in the luminescence emission spectra of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag

glasses. From a large number of studies [7–16,19–26] on Dy³⁺-activated oxide glasses with different compositions reviewed in the introduction, a similar band at 455 nm was observed only in lithium fluoroborate glass [8], where it was attributed to the $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{15/2}$ transition of Dy³⁺ ions. In the remaining 17 articles, this band is not observed or recorded. On the one hand, the observed band peaking at 452 nm in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses may correspond to the $^4I_{15/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{15/2}$ transition because, as will be shown below, the $^6H_{15/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{15/2}$ transition is located at 451 nm in luminescence excitation spectra. But on the other hand, as will be shown below, the decay time of the band peaking at 452 nm is similar to the decay time of the emission from the $^4F_{9/2}$ state. This is an unexpected result, because if the observed band peaking at 452 nm corresponds to the emission from the $^4I_{15/2}$ state, its decay time should be different from the decay time of the emission from the $^4F_{9/2}$ state. The energy difference between the emission bands peaking at 452 nm and 481 nm is 1334 cm^{-1} . This value is very close to the B–O stretching vibrations of the BO₃ units, which have an energy of 1385 cm^{-1} in the 0.33Li₂O–0.67B₂O₃ glass [29]. These stretching vibrations are the most intense and have the highest energy in the infrared spectrum of lithium borate glasses [29]. Therefore, the band peaking at 452 nm in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses can be the so-called phonon side band of the emission at 481 nm ($^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow ^6H_{15/2}$ transition).

Besides this, one can see a broad band peaking near 408 nm, which is well observed in the luminescence emission spectrum of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass and is absent in the spectrum of LiBO:Dy glass. This band belongs to the $4d^95s^1 \rightarrow 4d^{10}$ transition of Ag⁺ ions. This luminescence is discussed in detail in Subsection 3.3 below.

Luminescence excitation spectra of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses recorded by monitoring of the emission intensity at 574 nm are presented in Fig. 3. One can observe numerous narrow bands, which belong to the $4f - 4f$ transitions of Dy³⁺ ions labelled in Fig. 3. The transitions have been identified on the basis of the reference [28]. The most intense excitation band is located at 349 nm ($^6H_{15/2} \rightarrow ^6P_{7/2}$ transition). The intensity of the excitation bands in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass exceeds that in LiBO:Dy glass by approximately 15 – 50% in the UV–visible range and 50 – 100% in the

UV range of less than 330 nm. Consequently, the presence of Ag co-activator leads to an increase in the excitation efficiency of the Dy^{3+} luminescence.

Fig. 3. Luminescence excitation spectra of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glass recorded by monitoring of the emission intensity at 574 nm.

Besides the narrow $4f-4f$ transitions of Dy^{3+} ions, there is also a broad band near 265 nm in the luminescence excitation spectrum of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass. This band belongs to the $4d^{10} \rightarrow 4d^9 5s^1$ transition of Ag^+ ions. The observation of this excitation band suggests an energy transfer from Ag^+ ions to Dy^{3+} ions.

3.3. Luminescence emission and excitation spectra of Ag centres

Luminescence emission spectrum of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass recorded upon UV-C excitation ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 268$ nm) is presented in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the most intense Dy^{3+} emission bands at 481 nm and 574 nm lie on a very broad emission band ranging from 350 to 650 nm. The maximum of this broad band is located in the 450 – 470 nm range and overlaps with the $4F_{9/2} \rightarrow 6H_{15/2}$ transition of

Dy³⁺ ions. Therefore, the luminescence intensity at 440 nm was monitored during the recording of the luminescence excitation spectrum of the broad emission band. This monitoring wavelength allows to avoid narrow Dy³⁺ transitions in the luminescence excitation spectrum.

Fig. 4. Luminescence emission spectrum (solid curve) of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass recorded upon excitation at 268 nm and luminescence excitation spectrum (dashed curve) of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass recorded by monitoring of the emission intensity at 440 nm.

Corresponding luminescence excitation spectrum of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is presented in Fig. 4. The spectrum reveals two broad bands: stronger with a maximum at 348 nm and weaker with a maximum at 268 nm. These bands can be related to the excitation of Ag nanoclusters and Ag⁺ ions, respectively. Emission spectrum recorded upon $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 268$ nm is presented in Fig. 4 and described above. Emission spectrum recorded upon $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 348$ nm is almost identical to the spectrum (b) in Fig. 2, which was recorded upon excitation at 349 nm.

Let us return to the broad emission band in the 350 – 650 nm range in Fig. 4. It can be seen that this band is too broad to be attributed to a single band. In our opinion, the broad band is a

superposition of two bands peaking at 398 nm and 523 nm. These are approximate wavelength positions obtained with an uncertainty of few nm. The emission band peaking in the violet spectral range is attributed to the $4d^95s^1 \rightarrow 4d^{10}$ transition of the isolated Ag^+ ions. The emission band peaking in the cyan-green spectral range belongs to small non-plasmonic molecule-like Ag nanoclusters or aggregates, also known as Ag_m^{n+} centres. These assignments are supported by studies [17–19,30–33], where the luminescence properties of Ag^+ ions and Ag nanoclusters in oxide glasses have been reported.

3.4. Decay kinetics of Dy^{3+} ions and Ag centres

The decay kinetics of the most intense yellow Dy^{3+} emission band at 574 nm (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{13/2}$ transition) in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses are presented in Fig. 5. The recorded decay kinetics are slightly non-monoexponential. Therefore, the mean lifetime (τ_{mean}) was evaluated according to the formula:

$$\tau_{\text{mean}} = \frac{\int t \cdot I(t) \cdot dt}{\int I(t) \cdot dt}, \quad (2)$$

where $I(t)$ is the luminescence intensity at time t . The obtained τ_{mean} values are 819 μs and 803 μs for LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses, respectively.

The decay kinetics of the narrow emission band at 452 nm in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag are presented as inset in Fig. 5. The mean lifetimes of these decay kinetics are 841 μs and 801 μs for LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses, respectively. These lifetimes are not far away from the lifetimes of the emission from the ${}^4\text{F}_{9/2}$ state, suggesting that the band peaking at 452 nm can correspond to the phonon side band of the emission at 481 nm (${}^4\text{F}_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6\text{H}_{15/2}$ transition).

The decay kinetics of the broad Ag emission in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is presented in Fig. 6. There are three decay curves recorded at the monitoring wavelengths of 398 nm, 440 nm, and 523 nm. All decay curves are clearly non-monoexponential, but they can be fitted quite well by a sum of two exponents. The τ_1 and τ_2 values are 35 μs and 130 μs for 398 nm (decay curve (a) in Fig. 6), 52 μs and 300 μs for 440 nm (decay curve (b) in Fig. 6), and 59 μs and 306 μs for 523 nm (decay curve

(c) in Fig. 6). The decay times of the emissions at 440 nm and 523 nm are quite similar. The shape of the decay curves (b) and (c) at medium and long times is quite similar also. Some differences at short times can be caused by the contribution of short decay kinetics (decay curve (a)) to the decay curve (b) recorded at the monitoring wavelength of 440 nm. The amplitude-weighted average lifetime (τ_{avg}) for each decay curve was calculated as follows:

$$\tau_{avg} = \frac{A_1\tau_1 + A_2\tau_2}{A_1 + A_2}, \quad (3)$$

where A_1 and A_2 are the amplitudes of the τ_1 and τ_2 lifetimes, respectively. The obtained τ_{avg} values are 63 μ s, 124 μ s and 166 μ s for emission at 398 nm, 440 nm and 523 nm, respectively.

Fig. 5. Luminescence decay kinetics of emission at 574 nm (${}^4F_{9/2} \rightarrow {}^6H_{13/2}$ transition of Dy^{3+} ions) in LiBO:Dy (a) and LiBO:Dy,Ag (b) glasses recorded upon excitation at 349 nm (${}^6H_{15/2} \rightarrow {}^6P_{7/2}$ transition of Dy^{3+} ions). The inset presents luminescence decay kinetics of emission at 452 nm in LiBO:Dy (a) and LiBO:Dy,Ag (b) glasses recorded upon the same excitation at 349 nm.

Fig. 6. Luminescence decay kinetics of emission at 398 nm (a), 440 nm (b), and 523 nm (c) in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass recorded upon excitation at 268 nm.

From the obtained results we can assume that there are two types of Ag centres in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass. These are Ag^+ ions, which show emission in the violet spectral range, and Ag nanoclusters, which show emission in the cyan-green spectral range. The emission at 440 nm is not caused by a separate Ag centre but is a superposition of the above mentioned Ag^+ ions and Ag nanoclusters. The decay kinetics of Ag^+ ions is faster than that of Ag nanoclusters.

3.5. Chromaticity properties, luminescence quantum yield and energy transfer channels

The colours of the recorded emissions are presented in the CIE chromaticity diagram in Fig. 7. The emission colour of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses upon excitation at 349 nm is represented by the symbols “•” labelled 1 and 2, respectively. The chromaticity coordinates (x , y) are (0.3443, 0.3889) and (0.3341, 0.3771) for LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses, respectively. The obtained values are not far away from the standard white light (0.3333, 0.3333) of the CIE illuminant E. The correlated colour temperature (CCT) or T_c (K) was calculated using the McCamy approximation

[34]. For LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses upon excitation at 349 nm, the CCT equals 5115 K and 5442 K, respectively. The cooler white light for LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is caused by the presence of broad Ag luminescence in the blue spectral range (see Fig. 2). The Duv values, which describe how far the light colour point is from the black body curve, are 0.0179 and 0.0167 for LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses, respectively. The emission colour of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass upon excitation at 268 nm is represented by the symbol “•” labelled 3 (see Fig. 7). The corresponding chromaticity coordinates are (0.2476, 0.2979), the CCT is 12910 K, the Duv value is 0.0255. It is a blue-white light. Therefore, by changing the excitation wavelength, the emission of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass can be adjusted from white to blue-white.

Fig. 7. CIE chromaticity diagram. The symbols “•” labelled 1 and 2 correspond to the emission colour of LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses, respectively, recorded upon excitation at 349 nm. The symbol “•” labelled 3 corresponds to the emission colour of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass recorded upon excitation at 268 nm.

The quantum yield of luminescence is the ratio of the number of photons emitted to the number of photons absorbed. A high quantum yield indicates that a large proportion of the absorbed photons result in emission, making the luminescence process more efficient. Therefore, quantum yield is used as a selection criterion to evaluate the performance of luminescent materials for practical applications. The absolute or external quantum yield of the Dy³⁺ luminescence in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glass was measured experimentally using the integrating sphere. The results are presented in Table 2. It can be seen that the external quantum yield in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass increases from 13.4% to 15.1% comparing to LiBO:Dy glass. The increase in quantum yield in Ag-co-activated glass is the result of energy transfer from Ag⁺ ions and Ag nanoclusters to Dy³⁺ ions.

Table 2. External luminescence quantum yield of the Dy³⁺ emission in LiBO:Dy and LiBO:Dy,Ag glasses and some other Dy³⁺-activated materials.

Composition	Quantum yield, %	References
LiBO:Dy or 33Li ₂ O–66B ₂ O ₃ –1Dy ₂ O ₃ glass	13.4	this article
LiBO:Dy,Ag or 32.33Li ₂ O–64.66B ₂ O ₃ –1Dy ₂ O ₃ –2AgNO ₃ glass	15.1	this article
33BaO–66B ₂ O ₃ –1Dy ₂ O ₃ glass	8	[16]
33Li ₂ O–6.6Al ₂ O ₃ –59.4B ₂ O ₃ –1Dy ₂ O ₃ glass	9	[16]
2Na ₂ O–17Bi ₂ O ₃ –2PbO–19GeO ₂ –60TeO ₂ glass with 0.5Dy ₂ O ₃	9.72	[23]
2Na ₂ O–17Bi ₂ O ₃ –2PbO–19GeO ₂ –60TeO ₂ glass with 0.5Dy ₂ O ₃ and 0.5AgCl	10.61	[23]
45P ₂ O ₅ –15K ₂ O–10Al ₂ O ₃ –19BaF ₂ –10NaF ₂ –1Dy ₂ O ₃ glass	3	[35]
40BaO–20TiO ₂ –40SiO ₂ –0.5Dy ₂ O ₃ glass	4.1	[36]
23Na ₂ O–2MgO–22Al ₂ O ₃ –53GeO ₂ glass with Dy ₂ O ₃ (1.0 wt.%)	8.90	[37]
10Na ₂ O–4K ₂ O–10ZnO–6MgO–13TeO ₂ –57B ₂ O ₃ glass with Dy ₂ O ₃ (2.0 wt.%)	14.42	[38]
YVO ₄ nanoparticles with Dy ³⁺ (2 at.%)	7	[39]
Dy ³⁺ - activated Ba ₂ TiSi ₂ O ₈ nanocrystals	15.2	[36]

the obtained external quantum yield in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is higher than the quantum yield of the Dy³⁺ luminescence in barium borate [16], lithium aluminoborate [16], multicomponent germanotelurite [23], multicomponent phosphate [35], barium titanium silicate [36], multicomponent germanate [37], multicomponent telluroborate [38] glasses. Furthermore, our results of quantum yield are competitive with crystalline materials. In particular, the quantum yield in LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is higher than Dy³⁺-activated YVO₄ nanoparticles [39] and comparable with Dy³⁺-activated Ba₂TiSi₂O₈ nanocrystals [36]. Thus, LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is a promising luminescent material for the white spectral range. The simplicity of the preparation technology and the ability to produce large transparent luminescent layers are key advantages of the investigated borate glasses that cannot be achieved with powders and single crystals.

4. Conclusions

Dy-activated and Dy-Ag-co-activated lithium tetraborate glasses have been obtained and studied using optical absorption, photoluminescence emission and excitation spectra, photoluminescence decay kinetics, photoluminescence quantum yield measurements. After an analysis of the experimental results, it is possible to summarise them as follows:

- Dy and Ag activators are incorporated into the Li₂B₄O₇ glass network as Dy³⁺ (4f⁹) and Ag⁺ (4d¹⁰) ions and Ag nanoclusters (Ag_mⁿ⁺ centres).
- Luminescence emission and excitation bands and decay curves of Dy³⁺ and Ag⁺ ions and Ag nanoclusters were recorded, identified and discussed.
- In particular, the luminescence emission spectra reveal two strong narrow blue and yellow bands assigned to the ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_{15/2} and ⁴F_{9/2} → ⁶H_{13/2} transitions of Dy³⁺ ions and two broad unresolved bands in the violet-green spectral range related to Ag⁺ ions and Ag nanoclusters.
- The luminescence lifetimes are in the μs time range and decrease in the following order of luminescence centres: Dy³⁺ ions, Ag nanoclusters and Ag⁺ ions.
- LiBO:Dy,Ag glass shows higher luminescence intensity and greater luminescence quantum yield than LiBO:Dy glass.

- The energy transfer pathways Ag^+ ions \rightarrow Dy^{3+} ions and Ag nanoclusters \rightarrow Dy^{3+} ions were discussed.
- The chromaticity coordinates of LiBO:Dy,Ag glass are (0.3341, 0.3771) which is very close to the standard white light. The corresponding correlated colour temperature is 5442 K.
- The LiBO:Dy,Ag glass is a promising luminescent material for white emission.

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